

Listening Beyond Human Perception with Jez riley French and Pheobe riley Law

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Abstract

We are surrounded by countless sounds that lie outside the range of human hearing. Although not directly perceptible by humans, such sounds profoundly impact our planet's ecosystems and hold immense value for human and more-than-human lives. In this paper, I will first address the limitations of our hearing and reflect on how we can deepen our awareness of the sounds outside our hearing range: infra- and ultrasounds and quiet sounds. I will also consider how human listeners, including artists, have come to terms with sound worlds inaccessible via the human ear through whole-body, multi-sensory, micro and durational listening, and a variety of hearing assistive technologies. Then I will focus on British sound artists and field recordists Jez riley French and Pheobe riley Law who have extensively listened to airborne ultrasound including the vocalization of bats, subaquatic sounds, and subterranean sounds in soil horizons (including the sounds of trees). French and Law recorded these sounds with a wide range of self-built and adapted microphones to translate their listening experiences into music and media art. I will specifically discuss three of their works: "ultrasons | Edogawa" from *elusive fields* (2018), "a glacier heated by the sea" (2015), and "Cherry Birch from the *ink botanic* series (2020–). I argue that through the work of French, Law, and other artists in this field, we may gain a better understanding of acoustic ecology's hidden dimensions which are a register for our environments' health. We may rethink our own sonic perception and footprint and ideally be motivated to help sustain the planet's sonic futures.

This paper builds on my collaborative research with audiologists and field recordists at ASU's Acoustic Ecology Lab, work by scholars and artists such as Karen Bakker, Jez riley French, Steve Goodman, Stefan Helmreich, Toby Heys, and Pheobe riley Law. The paper seeks to advance discussions about small and inaudible environmental sounds and to introduce French and Law's work into the scholarly discourse.

1. Introduction

We humans are surrounded by countless and highly dynamic sonic webs that lie outside our hearing range, hidden acoustic ecologies. Even though we may fail to perceive, acknowledge, and appreciate such sounds, they increase auditory acuity within our audible spectrum, have a profound impact on our planet's ecosystems, and hold immense value for both human and more-than-human lives. In this essay, I will first address the limitations of human hearing and how we can broaden our awareness of the sounds beyond our hearing range: airborne, subterranean, and subaquatic sounds, biophonies, anthrophonies, and geophonies – sounds of

living and non-living matter.¹ I will also consider how human listeners, including artists, have come to terms with sound worlds inaccessible via the human ear through whole-body, multi-sensory, micro and durational listening, and a variety of hearing assistive technologies. Then I will take a closer look at British sound artists and field recordists Jez Riley French and Pheobe Riley Law who have extensively listened to airborne ultrasound including the vocalization of bats, subaquatic sounds, and subterranean sounds in soil horizons (including the sounds of trees). French and Law recorded these sounds with a wide range of self-built and adapted microphones to creatively translate their listening experiences for human listeners and thus encourage greater appreciation of our sonic environments' most subtle dimensions. I will specifically discuss three of their works: "ultrasons | Edogawa" from *elusive fields* (2018), "a glacier heated by the sea" (2015), and "Cherry Birch" from the *ink botanic* series (2020–). I argue that these and other artists not only unlock new possibilities for creative expression, but also advance a better understanding of acoustic ecology's hidden dimensions which are a register for our environments' health. This may make us rethink our own sonic perception and footprint and ideally be motivated to help sustain the planet's sonic futures.

2. Limitations of Human Hearing, Unheard Sounds, Sonic Conflicts

Humans often take their sense of hearing and hearing range (optimally encompassing circa 20–20,000 Hz above 20 microPascals) for granted and frequently focus their views of the world and actions on what they can and cannot hear (Brownell). Thus, they often overlook that their hearing is always selective, that they filter out sounds and that different forms of upbringing result in different physical and mental responses to their sonic environments. They also often disregard that their greatest acuity may only range between circa 2 and 4 kHz, as demonstrated by the A-weighted curve following the Fletcher-Munson contours. Moreover, humans tend to ignore that their hearing gradually deteriorates with increasing age and due to various life circumstances, including environmental factors, illness, and unsafe listening practices. Currently almost 500 million people across the globe have disabling hearing loss.² Thus, with the gradually shrinking range of what humans can hear, the scope of hidden acoustic ecologies broadens.

However, in addition to using their ears as auditory sensors, humans can also listen through their skin, a sensory organ detecting sound as vibrational energy. Indigenous people, such as the Kamayurá and Xinguano in South America, the hearing impaired, acoustic ecologists, and artists have explored multi-sensorial or inter-sensorial sound perception, including whole-body listening, to access otherwise inaudible sounds (Mori, pp. 25–43; Bastos, pp. 287–305). The near-deaf percussionist Evelyn Glennie senses sound with several body parts: low frequencies with her feet and legs (as solid materials such as floors can serve as transducers), and high sounds with her face, neck, and chest (Glennie).

Throughout the centuries, ever more refined hearing assistive technology, including ear trumpets, digital aids, ear implants, and recording devices, have helped humans to access inaudible sounds though they always act as filters. Early sound amplification and microphone developments were often driven by the search for hearing loss solutions, before being

¹ I am here referring to Bernie Krause's and Stuart Gage's well-established terms.

² "Disabling hearing loss" is defined by the World Health Organization as a loss that exceeds 35 dB in the better hearing ear.

advanced in the sciences, military, and arts. The severely hearing-impaired Thomas Edison pioneered one of the first (carbon) microphones. Today, artists and scientists use, besides multisensory listening, hearing assistive technologies to eavesdrop on hidden acoustic ecologies, often aiming at uncovering and studying the voices of endangered species and habitats.

Compared to many other species, humans with optimal hearing can detect only a fraction of their sonic environments, and, unaware of the “real’s” actual scope, construct their reality accordingly. They cannot hear infrasound, frequencies below 20 Hz from volcanoes, earthquakes, and thunderstorms, which pigeons, elephants, and baleen whales can hear. Elephants and baleen whales, for instance, emit and perceive infrasound to communicate with distant mates. Even more animals, bats, cats, dogs, and insects, can produce and hear ultrasound, sounds above 20 kHz. The greater wax moths can hear up to 300 kHz allowing them to escape such predators as bats.

Humans also generate manifold infra- and ultrasounds despite being unable to hear them without tools. Home appliances, radios, nuclear testing, and military and industrial machinery, including sonic weapons (Long Range Acoustic Devices), produce infrasound. Sonar devices and pest and algae control systems, for instance, generate ultrasound.

Besides infra- and ultrasounds, humans cannot hear frequencies, whose pressure level is below 20 microPascals. These include the sounds of butterflies, jellyfish, and worms, among the planet’s quietest animals. Nor can they hear the sounds of plants. Falsely perceived to be deaf and mute, plants, including corn, cacti, and tomatoes, emit and receive sounds between circa 10 and 250 Hz, especially when under stress. Unlike humans, wolves, dogs, and cats among others can detect very quiet and far away sounds.

In recent decades, more and more musicians, partly inspired by John Cage’s silent piece *4’33’’* and Morton Feldman’s quiet aesthetics, have created sparse-textured music hovering at the threshold of human hearing. They include artists from the Wandelweiser group (founded in 1992 and including Antoine Beuger, Jürg Frey, Eva-Maria Houben, Michael Pisaro, and Mark So) (Ross). Similarly, Taylor Deuprée, Rolf Julius, and Steve Roden associated with the lowercase, microsound and/or small music trends have specialized in acoustic, electronic and/or field-recording-based or very quiet sounds creating subtle types of ambient music. Once known as a loud violinist, Monica Germino now explores very quiet repertoire involving mutes or the “whisperviolin” following a hyperacusis diagnosis (extreme sound sensitivity). Acoustic ecologist Gordon Hempton created *One Square Inch of Silence*, a project to find and protect the quietest places in America (Hempton). The online platform *Below 20: Sound Museum of Silence*, among several physical and virtual venues focused on silence, gathers field recordings and musical pieces with a sound pressure level below 20 decibels. Sound artist Jez riley French explores “micro-listening” focusing on the smallest sounds in a space as they convey “an intense sense of the ambience they are part of” (Fischer and Cory, pp. 38–39).

While the artists and trends above protest the rising decibel levels and proliferation of anthropogenic sounds on our planet and music’s use as sonic torture in prisons, they rarely consider the realms of infra- and ultrasonics. But human insensitivity toward hidden acoustic ecologies – air-borne, subaquatic and subterranean – have changed environments and harmed life on our planet. For instance, infrasound emitted by ever larger numbers of oceanic freight ships has shrunk the communication radius of whales and other species (Bakker, pp. 36–37). The low frequencies at harmful sound pressure levels of seismic testing and high intensity

sonar activities for oil and gas exploration and military purposes have impaired the communication and wellbeing of whales, dolphins, and squid among other species (Horwitz). Designed to deter unwelcome insects and rodents, ultrasonic pest repellents, although not reliably efficacious, distress dogs, hamsters, and young adult humans. Ultrasound exceeding 120 decibels can damage human hearing (AGNIR). The loud and low frequencies of infrasonic weapons (Long Range Acoustic Devices, LRAD) designed to repel crowds and pirates cause severe nausea and digestive problems in humans (Heys, 225–231). Such infrasonic and ultrasonic waves not only impact human and non-human health, but also lead to species migration and extinction, thus substantially transforming ecosystems. One way of building awareness of our planet's hidden sonic dimensions is through an engagement with music and sound art inspired by hidden airborne, subaquatic and subterranean acoustic ecologies.

3. Expanding the Borders of Human Listening: Jez riley French and Phoebe riley Law

Among the artists dedicated to unnoticed and unheard acoustic ecologies are Jez riley French (b. 1965), a musician, sound artist, and photographer, and his daughter Pheobe riley Law (b. 1997), a multimedia artist specializing in sound installation, film, and sculpture. Based in the UK, both artists have practiced listening to a wide variety of environments since childhood. French became a passionate environmental listener and field recordist by accident.³ At age twelve, he received a portable tape recorder from his mother and unwittingly discovered his back garden's rich sound world by recording it, pressing, by mistake, the device's record (instead of its play) button. He instilled his love of listening in his daughter early on. Unlike Schafer, French and Law embrace anthrophonies, biophonies, and geophonies as equitable and enmeshed components of sonic environments and refrain from ranking them as preferable or objectionable, as hi-fi or lo-fi environments, or as examples of noise pollution. Rather than listening to sounds analytically and semantically to identify sound sources, signals, soundmarks, or keynote and archetypal sounds, they prefer to experience sound somatically and as a medium. French (2021) emphasizes that "we must resist the drift towards an imposition of an elitist, privileged view of sound on the world." Being aware of each listener's unique listening background and his own privileged status as a white male artist, he finds it "bizarre that we think of ourselves as aware of racial, gender or physical/neuro-ability-based biases, oppose them, speak out against them and yet are comfortable with a very small handful of disproportionately white and still largely male academics defining, framing, and taking ownership of sound and listening for the world" (2021).

French and Law have intensely listened to "sounds above, below, and outside our attention," especially the resonant realms beyond the human hearing range (French 2021). These include, on the one hand, hidden resonances of fences, bridges, wind turbines, churches, museums, spaces between buildings, staircases, domestic lightbulbs, and antennas in remote forests and, on the other hand, sounds of melting glaciers, trees, moss, ants munching overripe fruit, and periwinkles eating seagrass. French and Law do not "ascribe to the separation of species" often implied by using the concept of nature. To French (2021) a

³ Environmental listening denotes listening to urban and non-urban environments, extending beyond the act of listening to what is traditionally understood as music.

“recording of a table in Kettle’s Yard is as much about nature as one of any elements in any environment that has been shaped by other living entities.” French and Law have listened in local, national, and international places and spaces from Yorkshire, England, their home base, across Great Britain and Europe to Japan, Korea, and Australia.

French and Law engage in what they call “listening underneath,” listening to the inner vibrations of surfaces, to subterranean and subaquatic sounds for which they often use very sensitive contact microphones, hydrophones, and/or geophones. French traces this type of listening practice back to the 1970s when he, for instance, paid close attention to the subtly changing hum of his bedroom walls and the creaking timber when his home was cooling down or warming up (2021). He and his daughter also practice micro- or quantum listening, listening to very quiet sounds at and beyond the threshold of audibility with and without hearing assistive technology, for instance, the “audible silence” of architecture. Furthermore, French and Law explore durational listening which may last hours or extend, with interruptions, to several years. This can be focused on a single place, situation, or object, and allows them to hear more, become aware of the intensity of their sonic surroundings and develop an emotive sense of place and a palpable presence in time and place. In fact, French notes that durational listening, “outside the limits of normal attention,” permits place or a situation to impose itself on them (2021). Building on their rich and detailed sonic memories, French and Law have also collaboratively experimented with the soundtracking of photographs and created a series of *Scores for Listening*, more or less abstract photographs serving as a memory aid and score for themselves or as an inspiration for other listeners to imagine sounds or translate them into audible sounds.⁴ Sometimes they add text to the photographs or create autonomous text scores with further guidance for listening and performance as in *entice new normality*.⁵

These different modes of listening have informed French’s and Law’s approaches to field recording. French states that he often makes recordings “through memory, photographs, text, [and] experience” and only “sometimes by the use of audio recording equipment.” (2021). He and his daughter consider their audio recordings merely as “traces” of their interactions with place (2021). Therefore, they often share only short audio or audio-visual excerpts from much longer recordings as audio tracks or included in various media art works, hoping to thwart objectification and a kind of sonic colonization of environments (2021). Yet he established himself internationally as a field recordist and a user and builder of high-quality microphones (hand-made from ethically sourced materials), sold to and sought after in various music industries greatly advancing the practice of field recording.⁶ He started building his own contact microphones and hydrophones as a teenager, gradually broadened the palette of self-designed and -built recording equipment and is now joined by his daughter in this endeavour. Together they explore what French calls “intuitive” and “extended” recording techniques, intentionally ignoring audio engineering textbook rules (2021). For infrasound recordings, “inaccessible in their raw state,” French and Law use self-built infrasound-

⁴ For examples see: <https://jezrileyfrench.co.uk/scores-for-listening.php>.

⁵ Jez riley French and Pheobe riley Law, *score for listening: entice new normality* (2020) (<https://jezrileyfrench.co.uk/scores-for-listening.php>). Accessed 20 February 2025.

⁶ French’s microphones are praised for their high quality and affordability and widely used in radio, theatre, TV, films video games, and academia.

achieving contact microphones and adapted and non-adapted commercial higher specification geophones (2021).⁷ For ultrasound recordings, they employ ultrasonic detectors and electromagnetic coils. They also use surround and ambisonic microphone arrays, and since 2010, they have recorded weather events including lightning strikes with Very Low Frequency (VLF) receivers which allow for audio representation of radio fallout in the ionosphere and magnetosphere.

When making field trips and recordings French often ponders how we often unconsciously apply various auditory filters to our listening and “how environments are reduced and controlled by the narratives we impose on them.” (2021). Besides hosting field recording workshops, French and Law regularly share their experience as listeners and field recordists with other artists and general audiences to “explore together the act and art of located sound” in specifically themed and curated field listening and recording trips called *murmuration* gatherings (2018–).⁸ These experientially rich gatherings underpinned by environmental advocacy are eminently instructive and can be seen as alternative forms of sound and music education for people from different social and cultural backgrounds. French and Law do not create sound maps or sound banks but prefer to weave largely unedited field recordings into their intuitively composed and unconventionally notated music, improvisations, and installations. Largely self-taught as a composer, French became aware of *musique concrète* and other explorative, intuitive, and expansive compositional approaches in the early 1980s, which informed his work made with guitars, synthesizers, and tape. In more recent years, he has expanded his artistic practice through collaborations with Law who has a degree in Fine Arts and is an installation artist working with sound. Among French and Law’s most fascinating creative endeavours are their explorations of hidden airborne, subaquatic, and subterranean acoustic ecologies which will be discussed below.

4. Hidden Airborne Sounds

French and Law have listened to and recorded ultrasonics for several decades and drawn our attention to the existence of ultrasound in both indoor and outdoor environments. Through *audible silence: tate modern, sleeping and waking* (2019), an installation and digital audio album, French has allowed us to eavesdrop on ultrasound emitted by lighting systems in buildings such as the Tate Modern art gallery in London.⁹ In *island | fjórar (geothermal activity)* (2015) and *island | fjórar – the crystal detector* (2020–21), which are part of the *island | fjórar* series (2013–) including installations, performance-based diffusions, FM soundwalks, photographic and text scores for listening, and digital audio tracks, French and Law let us tune into the ultrasonics of geothermal activity in Iceland.¹⁰ They have also helped raise awareness of ultrasonic insect and bat vocalization.

⁷ See French’s notes on *in limitless geologies* at <https://jezrileyfrench.co.uk/in-limitless-geologies.php>.

⁸ See <https://jezrileyfrench.co.uk/murmuration.php>. Topics of previous *murmuration* gatherings include diffusion and installation, interspecies-collaboration, remote monitoring, and transmission. <https://jezrileyfrench.co.uk/workshops---gatherings.php>.

⁹ For listening examples see <https://engravedglass.bandcamp.com/album/audible-silence-tate-modern-sleeping-and-waking> and <https://soundcloud.com/jezrileyfrench/tate-modern-ultrasonics>.

¹⁰ Listen to an excerpt of French and Law’s *the crystal detector* here: <https://jezrileyfrench.co.uk/the-crystal-detector.php>.

French first experienced ultrasonics in the 1980s, used a do-it-yourself ultrasound detector in the 2000s, and thereafter attained a high-quality ultrasound detector from Petterson Elektronik AB to listen to the echolocation of bats (French, *elusive fields*, nd). Demonized in Western culture, bats are highly vocal animals. Having poor vision, they use ultrasonic vocalization by mouth and nose in echolocation for navigation and food hunting. They also use communicative calls and sing territorial and courtship songs which baby bats learn from adults and then evolve into large and distinct regional repertoires (Daley 2016). Bat sounds have been closely studied by scientists since the 1990s when modern ultrasonic detectors could pick them up, visualize them or translate them into human hearing range. Bat sounds have also been featured in media art when portable digital bat detectors, along with appropriate ultrasonic microphones, became widely available and affordable for artists in the 2010s.¹¹

French and Law have contributed to this growing body of works. Good examples include French's "parabolic ultrasonic near river" (6:53), part of his album *suketchi* (2011–13), a series of "traces of two trips to Japan," as well as "ultrasons | Edogawa" (11:51) from his album *elusive fields* (2018), also made from field recordings in Japan (Edogawa is a special ward in Tokyo).¹² "parabolic ultrasonic near river" presents a rich multilayered waxing and waning texture of biophonies, geophonies, and anthrophonies. Distinctly rhythmic, bright, and high staccato tones of bats alternate with the subtle high-frequency tremoli of fast-moving nocturnal insects around streetlights and are occasionally punctuated by loud resonant crackles. A gentle pink noise drone and continuous high-pitched gurgles of river water provide a foundation for the lively sonic strands throughout. In "ultrasons | Edogawa," the bats, probably Japanese house, northern or short tailed bats native in Tokyo, are the soloists as their rhythmically animated and timbrally strident sound patterns prominently unfold over a dynamically wavering white noise drone reminiscent of radio static.

French emphasized that his goal was not to create heavily edited "audio portraits" of specific places from a conventional audio engineering perspective (involving foregrounding of wanted sound and aesthetically motivated minimization of unwanted sound), but to listen through technology while acknowledging one's intuitive responses to all sounds. Listening to bats through an ultrasonic detector, however, means that the sounds humans hear are substantially transformed, given the quickness of bat calls (lasting milliseconds), the bats' huge frequency range (9–200 kHz), amplitude levels, and the simultaneity of multiple songs and calls (Jones and Holderied 2007). In general, ultrasonic detectors transpose bat frequencies downward, decelerate their rhythms, and change their sound pressure levels to accommodate human hearing. Varying in quality, bat detectors' frequency ranges are often smaller than those of bat sounds. These compromises notwithstanding, both "parabolic ultrasonic near river" and "ultrasons | Edogawa" are important reminders of the fact that 90% of endemic bat species in Japan are threatened with extinction (Preble et al. 2021). As few humans are aware of the musicality of bats, these acousmatic pieces draw attention to the mesmerizing vocalization of these ecologically crucial flying nocturnal mammals and to the large networks of heard and unheard sounds that surround us day and night.

¹¹ Other musicians who have used ultrasound in their works include Annea Lockwood, Steve Parker, Zach Poff, Karen Power, and Eisuke Yanagisawa.

¹² Both albums are available through French's engraved glass label on Bandcamp.

5. Hidden Subaquatic Sounds

French and Law have also extensively listened to and reflected on underwater sounds and done much to expand our awareness of it through subaquatic field recording-based art. French's fascination with underwater acoustics goes back to his teenage years when he came across oceanographer, marine biologist, and bioacoustics pioneer Marie Poland Fish's book *The Sounds of Western North Atlantic Fishes: A Reference File of Biological Underwater Sounds* (1970) and early albums with recordings of humpback whale songs, probably made by Katharine and Roger Payne and Frank Watlington.¹³ Poland Fish was among the first scientists who in the early 1950s used modern hydrophones, piezoelectric devices, to record marine wildlife for research purposes. Often inaudible above the water surface, underwater sounds travel much faster than airborne sounds, and subaquatic environments can be quite loud and sonorous, despite being falsely considered as "silent worlds."¹⁴ Subaquatic acoustic ecologies are highly dynamic and, unfortunately, often affected by overfishing, pollution, acidification, and rising temperatures. Sounds from navy sonar, seismic air guns, and ever-increasing freight ship traffic have not only drastically raised the decibel levels of ocean acoustics, but also displaced, injured, and killed many marine animals depending on sound for communication and navigation in a dark environment (Ocean Conservation Research nd).

French began building his first hydrophones in the 1980s to record sounds travelling through liquids and discover what it sounds like when a tide slowly fills a scaffolding pipe submerged in a river (French 2012). Over the next decades he built a variety of hydrophones for both fresh and saltwater environments (JrF d-series), which can pick up a wide range of sounds, including those of fish and aquatic insects and plants. French and Law have submerged hydrophones in diverse bodies of water: ponds, lakes, streams, seas, and oceans across the globe.

In the 2010s, French made several trips to Iceland, celebrated for its diverse bodies of water, including the Arctic and Atlantic Oceans, rivers, waterfalls, lakes, geysers, and glaciers. There, he led workshops and made extended underwater recordings. In June 2014, in Húsaik harbor at the Skálfandi Bay, a tourist destination for whale watching, French recorded the polyrhythmic delicate bell-like tinkles and bubbles, popping seaweed, the cod's short grunts, and snapping shrimp among many other unidentified underwater sounds.¹⁵ However, for French the identification of sound sources is secondary and must not get in the way of his emotive responses to sound in the act of listening. Soon after, French visited some of Iceland's glaciers and experienced the sonic outcomes of climate change-induced accelerated glacial corrosion and calving which poignantly manifest themselves via hydrophone-assisted listening. French's "a glacier heated by the sea" (2015–) which exists as a multi-channel audio work, a concert version, and an installation, makes strikingly audible the retreat of the Breiðamerkurjökull glacier and expansion of the Jökulsárlón glacial lake with sounds ranging from fizzy bursting air bubbles, gentle high-pitched chirps, hissing and cracking to thundering

¹³ See *Songs of the Humpback Whale*, produced by Roger and Katy Payne (CRM Records, 1970).

¹⁴ Jacques Cousteau's 1953 undersea discovery memoir, for instance, is titled *The Silent World*.

¹⁵ A short audio-visual excerpt from a longer recording of "island | harbour" can be found here: <https://vimeo.com/108555561>.

booms when large chunks of ice collapse into the water. According to French, “this piece asks us to consider not only the effects of global warming but the shift in acidity / salinity in the inter-connected realms of water: marshes, rivers, lakes, ice, rainfall and oceans. We listen in on 10,000-year-old air being released as glaciers melt, lava rock dissolved by river water, micro-communications of aquatic species and erosion of tide lines” (French, “a glacier heated by the sea,” nd).¹⁶ French has made further recordings that feature sounds of melting glaciers, including “jökulsárlón ultrasonics” (video, 5:43, 2015) and “fjallsárlón” (video, 6:36, 2016), the latter titled after the growing lagoon at Vatnajökull glacier.¹⁷ While Law did not join French on these field recording trips, she contributed text and added sonic and tonal elements to some of the pieces that resulted from his sojourns in Iceland.

In Iceland, glaciers have had a powerful physical and spiritual presence. In various Indigenous traditions of the polar regions, they are considered as awe-inspiring beings with agency, as beings that listen and smell, although in recent years they have become increasingly vulnerable much like endangered animal and plant species (Cruikshank 2005, 3–4, 6).

6. Hidden Subterranean Sounds

French and Law have extensively listened to subterranean sound worlds. Out of sight, these sounds are often too high, too low, and too quiet for human hearing and perhaps because of this fact, Schafer rarely addressed underground sounds in his writings, apart from categorizing mines, caves, tunnels, rocks, stones, subterranean vibrations, and trees as “sounds of earth” (1973, 139-40). But soil is home to many soniferous organisms – plants, fungi, microorganisms, insects, worms, and small mammals – as well as vibrations from water, seismic, and volcanic and human activity, for instance, that contribute to a subterranean acoustic ecology. Listeners above ground include mammals, birds, and insects that eavesdrop on soil sounds for communication and food detection purposes. But the naked human ear may need technological help to access many of them.

Recent trends such as biotremology and soil ecoacoustics research build on old geoscience which used geophones, seismometers, and seismographs, all passive sensors, capturing sounds from quakes, volcanoes, and explosions (Roberts and Wickings 2022). While the earliest of these devices date back to ancient China, modern sensors were pioneered in nineteenth-century Europe (Dewey and Byerly, 1969).¹⁸ Thanks to their high functionality, power efficiency, and portability, digital geophones, active sensors, became widely available in the 2000s. These geophones, along with contact microphones and hydrophones buried in the ground, have not only facilitated new scientific insight into the sound emission and reception of such organisms as plants, but they have also inspired musicians to explore and celebrate their sounds.

¹⁶ A short audio-visual excerpt from a longer recording of “island | harbour” can be found here: <https://vimeo.com/108555561>.

¹⁷ An audio excerpt of this piece can be found here: <https://jezrileyfrench.co.uk/a-glacier-heated-by-the-sea---2015-on-going.php/>.

¹⁸ Dewey and Byerly (1969) among others credit Chang Hêng for having invented one of the earliest seismoscopes in 132 A.D.

French and Law have made subterranean recordings with infrasound-sensitive contact microphones with higher specification recorders/pre-amps and impedance adaptors, adapted and non-adapted, commercial, higher spec geophones with modified and unmodified digital recorders and self-created software. But French also listens to infrasound without assistive technology. He finds that “it is possible to sense the physical impact of infrasound,” which can be challenging because “we learn to ignore or filter out a vast range of the frequencies, further limited by our physical auditory capacities, paying attention only when they become disputed or disruptive” (French, engraved glass, nd). He also observes that “our systems of community often limit our senses further. We live in buildings that vibrate, on ground that is resonated by the earth turning on its axis, shifted at microscopic levels by myriad species in the soil. If we listen in to these deep, grounding vibrations we can begin to unravel fictions of place, our acceptance and reliance on structures of knowledge, archive and status that favour our species” (French, engraved glass, nd).

French and Law have dedicated multiple sets and series (some of them still in progress) to their subterranean listening. These include French and Law’s *moss listening* (2023) and French’s *in limitless geologies* (2023), *soil horizons* (2020–), *ink botanic* (2020–) and *The Secret Sounds of Trees* (2023), and Law’s current multi-platform work *vegetal empathy* (2025–). *in limitless geologies # 1* and *#2* (both 2023), for instance, comprises two digital albums with seven tracks each focusing on infrasound.¹⁹ All the tracks feature field recordings either made in Iceland or the U.K. between 2010 and 2022 using JrF adapted industrial geophones and software, plus a hacked recorder. Most tracks consist of raw recordings of located sound and should not be understood as audio documentaries of specific environments, rather as “traces filtered through technologies and choices” (French, *in limitless geographies* nd). The opening track of each album, however, is a lengthy composition, lasting forty and thirty minutes respectively. The quiet and meditative first piece of *in limitless geologies #1*, for example, uses located infrasound from Iceland as compositional material along with guitar and synthesizer sounds and clear inputs recorded with the same geophones used for the Icelandic field recordings which greatly adds to the piece’s eery quality. Tranquilly pulsing, quivering and dynamically fluctuating low rumbles and rustles are in the foreground of this slow-paced composition whose texture thickens through the gradual addition of waxing and waning sustained and resonant instrumental tones in its second half.²⁰

ink botanic (2020–) is a continuing series of multichannel audio works and installations, which explores the sounds of plants and soil layers: “transpiration, root systems, cavitation, vibrations in soil horizons, and situated connections between species and conceptual systems” (French, *ink botanic* nd). For “Cherry Birch,” part of *ink botanic*, French listened to a cherry birch in its habitat in a private arboretum in East Yorkshire, England on a rainy day. Equipped with a range of self-designed and adapted microphones, French recorded a vertical soundscape: sounds from around and inside the tree, vegetation above ground, and from the tree roots, organisms, and water in the topsoil, subsoil, and parent material. “Cherry Birch” (Soundcloud, 3:18) features the gentle murmurs of the tree absorbing rainwater through its roots in the soil horizons while birds, fungi, little creatures

¹⁹ *in limitless geologies* was inspired by Law who also came up with the title of the two works.

²⁰ Jez riley French’s *in limitless geologies 1* is available on Bandcamp and listening with headphones is highly recommended: <https://engravedglass.bandcamp.com/album/in-limitless-geologies-1-geophonic-works>.

(earthworms, tardigrades, nematodes, rotifers, springtails, woodlice, mites, centipedes, ants) in the soil and on the soil surface, in the moss and ferns add a multi-layered fabric of low and middle-range frequencies in nuanced timbres – rubbing, crackling, and rustling.²¹ Marked by both regular and irregular rhythms, the piece starts with a small and bright frequency range which in the second half broadens to include deeper and more voluminous sounds focusing our ears on the cherry birch’s vertical sonic dimensions.

French (2021) states that “the sounds of plants are much more fascinating, and challenging to our perception of them, than we have yet to realise. As the technologies become more accessible, we can, perhaps, learn to respect and represent creative ecologies with more equity, understanding that systems that thrive depend on roots and soil, not only the eye-catching foliage.” French and Law are among a growing number of artists who, through subterranean listening, have nudged us to soften our often heavy and harsh footprint in acknowledgement of our planet’s gentlest voices.²²

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, experiencing hidden acoustic ecologies – airborne, subaquatic, subterranean sounds beyond our hearing ranges – makes us question our alleged position of dominance and control on this planet, consider our limited sonic ways of knowing, and ponder a better sense of the realities that are imperceptible to us – even as our hearing range is shrinking. These sonic realities, although apparently separate from our own, are deeply interconnected with the perceptible ones and crucial for our own sonic futures. Indeed, these hidden and rapidly changing sound worlds are a register of the health of our perceptible environments, deserving greater human attention and sensitivity. Through inclusive and open-minded durational listening to the infinite details of sounds, including those “above, below and outside our attention” (French 2021), French and Law have broadened our contextual and experiential horizons, effectively sharing their listening and field recording experiences in a wide variety of media art, community field trips, and workshops. While ecoacousticians have driven conservation and industry and military policy changes through the monitoring of hidden sounds, much needs to be done to turn the public toward attentive, inclusive, and relational listening. Through that, we will be better equipped to understand our sonic perception and footprint, strengthen our planet’s health, and sustain its sonic futures.

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²¹ Jez riley French’s “cherry birch” from *ink botanic* is available on Soundcloud and listening with headphones is highly recommended, see <https://soundcloud.com/jezrileyfrench/tree-inner-sounds-testing-prototypes-of-jrf-plant-microphones>.

²² Other artists who engaged in subterranean listening and recording include Karine Bonneval (*Listen to the Soil*, n.d.), John Bullitt (*Deep Earth Dome*, 2006–), Bill Fontana (*Desert Soundings*, 2014), Nikki Lindt (*The Underground Sound Project*, 2018–), Marcus Maeder (*Sounding Soil*, 2019–), and Amy Youngs (*The Worms*, 2015).

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